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Countdown To 2030: Analyzing The Awareness Of The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) Among The Staff Of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study assesses the awareness, understanding, and engagement with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) among the staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic (HUKP), Nigeria, focusing on their role in promoting sustainable practices and education. Using a mixed-methods approach, the research analyzes data from surveys and interviews with academic, administrative, and technical staff. Findings reveal that while there is a foundational awareness of the SDGs among HUKP staff, there are notable gaps in detailed knowledge and practical engagement, especially in applying specific SDG targets within their professional roles. Key barriers identified include limited access to resources, lack of institutional support and minimal engagement initiatives. Recommendations emphasize the need for enhanced training, the integration of SDGs into institutional policies, and partnerships that foster sustainability. This study underscores the role of educational institutions in advancing the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and suggests strategies to improve SDG awareness and engagement in higher education contexts within Nigeria.

Keywords: Awareness, HUKP Staff, Sustainable Development Goals.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In the wake of global challenges such as climate change, poverty, inequality, and environmental degradation, the international community has come together to adopt the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as a blueprint for achieving a sustainable and equitable future by 2030. These 17 interconnected goals provide a framework for addressing pressing societal and environmental issues while promoting economic prosperity and social inclusion. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) succeed the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and are widely recognized as Agenda 2030, marking the targeted year for global attainment of the SDGs (UN 2017). During its existence, the MDGs served as a focal point for the world's developmental agenda, fostering innovative partnerships and contributing significantly to development in both developing and developed countries (UN 2015). In comparison, the SDGs present a more expansive agenda, comprising 17 goals, 169 targets, and over 200 indicators (IAEG-SDGs 2016). The SDGs embody a comprehensive framework centered around five "Ps": people, prosperity, planet, peace, and partnership, intended for

all nations and peoples worldwide (UNDP, 2016) Prior to the establishment of the SDGs, extensive global consultations were conducted among various stakeholders, including governments, civil society organizations, the private sector, scientists, academics, and individual citizens. The educational sector played a crucial role in these consultations, ensuring its inclusion and relevance in the formulation of the SDGs. Education, with its central focus on SDG enlightenment, plays a pivotal role in achieving the SDGs, akin to how Health Education is central to Primary Health Care. UNESCO recognizes education as a key factor in sustainable development, stating, "Sustainable development cannot be achieved by technological solutions, political regulation, or financial instruments alone. We need to change the way we think and act. This requires quality education and learning for sustainable development at all levels and in all social contexts" (UNESCO 2017)

African countries, including Nigeria, reportedly experienced a slow start in pursuing the MDGs, which posed a significant obstacle to their achievement (MDGs 2015, UN 2014) This slow start may have been attributed, at least in part, to the initial low level of awareness and knowledge about the MDGs among the populace. It is plausible that with heightened societal awareness, stakeholders from diverse sectors can advocate for the implementation of global development plans at the national level.

1.1 Nigeria's Educational and Developmental Challenges: Navigating Towards the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Nigeria continues to face significant obstacles in delivering quality education to its population. The nation's education system is burdened by issues such as inadequate infrastructure, a shortage of qualified teachers, and a high number of out-of-school children. Additionally, gender disparities and the lack of access to educational opportunities for marginalized communities hinder progress toward achieving quality education. In order to address these persistent challenges, the Nigerian government must prioritize education funding, introduce comprehensive teacher training programs, and ensure that educational policies are inclusive of all citizens. Oweibia et al. (2014) provides a detailed analysis of Nigeria's progress towards the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) since their inception. The study highlights the nation's efforts to integrate the SDGs into its development plans, acknowledging partial success in areas like policy alignment and strategic planning. However, challenges such as inequality, corruption, and inefficient implementation continue to hamper significant advancements. As one of the most populous countries in Africa and a major oil producer, Nigeria's role is crucial in the successful implementation of the SDGs, especially within the West African region. In 2015, the United Nations Member States adopted the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), a global initiative aimed at addressing pressing social, economic, and environmental challenges. The SDGs expanded on the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), established in 2000 and concluded in 2015 (Morufu et al., 2021; Raimi et al., 2020; Adedoyin et al., 2020; Olalekan et al., 2020). As a pivotal member of the United Nations, Nigeria plays a vital role in the global implementation of these goals. Despite its wealth in natural resources and cultural diversity, the country faces widespread socio-economic inequalities, political instability, corruption, and poverty (Morufu et al., 2021; Raimi et al., 2020; FGN, 2017; World Bank, 2021).

Recognizing the SDGs' comprehensive framework, which addresses poverty, education, gender equality, clean energy, economic growth, and climate action, Nigeria has aligned its national development strategies with these global objectives. One such example is the National Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP), which demonstrates the nation's strategic commitment to sustainable development (UN 2017; Sylvester et al., 2023; Saliu et al., 2023; Afolabi et al., 2021).

1.2 Overcoming Nigeria's Barriers to Inclusive and Equitable Quality Education

Nigeria faces significant challenges in ensuring inclusive and equitable access to quality education, particularly for girls and rural populations. As of 2018, the net primary school enrollment rate had fallen to 61.7%, down from 72.8% in 2010, leaving over a third of Nigerian children without access to basic education (Olalekan, et al. 2020; UNESCO, 2020). Multiple, complex factors contribute to this crisis, including insufficient education budgets, a shortage of schools, and a lack of trained teachers and functional facilities. Rural communities are particularly affected, with many lacking usable classrooms, learning materials, and access to technology. Additionally, insecurity caused by insurgencies disrupts schooling, while socio-cultural pressures disproportionately affect girls, reinforcing cycles of underinvestment and poverty (Olalekan, et al. 2020; UNESCO, 2020). To address these issues, Nigeria must undertake urgent reforms, including increased education funding,

decentralized management, enhanced teacher training, and the use of low-cost technologies. Targeted efforts are also needed to support impoverished or conflict-affected regions. Strong political will and community involvement are essential to reinforcing education's role in national development.

The country's education system suffers from chronic underfunding, with only 6% of the national budget allocated to education, far below UNESCO's recommended 15% (UNESCO, 2020). This underinvestment limits infrastructure development, leading to poorly equipped classrooms and inadequate learning materials. Additionally, the shortage of qualified teachers, especially in rural areas, hampers the delivery of quality education (UNESCO, 2020). Dilapidated facilities, a lack of clean water, and poor sanitation further discourage students from attending school regularly, reducing overall educational outcomes (Raimi, et al. 2019; Olalekan, et al. 2019, 2018). Tackling these barriers requires a holistic, multi-sectoral approach, including conditional cash transfers, free meals, improved infrastructure, and addressing socio-cultural factors like early marriage that prevent girls from completing their education. Only with concerted efforts from the government, civil society, and international partners can Nigeria hope to achieve Sustainable Development Goal 4: inclusive and equitable quality education for all. (Olalekan, et al. 2020; UNESCO, 2020; Raimi, et al. 2019)

1.3 Assessing Awareness and Engagement with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): Implications for Nigeria

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) represent a time-bound global development framework comprising 17 goals that target approximately 169 social, economic, and political indicators, revolving around the '5 Ps': People, Planet, Prosperity, Peace, and Partnership. Unlike its predecessor, the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), the SDGs adopt a more intricate and ambitious approach to development. As a global agenda, the SDGs create new avenues for collaboration and engagement among both state and non-state actors, responding to the pressing challenges of sustainable development. The global demand for human development and the need to build on the achievements of the MDGs shaped the 2030 Agenda and the SDGs. Karns et al. (2015) note that while work on the MDGs was ongoing, diplomats and experts began formulating goals for the subsequent fifteen years. The SDGs represent a collective commitment from world leaders to undertake shared actions across a broad, inclusive, and universal policy agenda. Together, these leaders and their nations embarked on a journey toward sustainable development, dedicating resources to pursue global development and foster "win-win" cooperation, particularly benefitting the African continent and its people.

The SDGs aim to build on the eight MDGs, which were established by world leaders during a UN summit in 2000. The transition from MDGs to SDGs offers a chance to tackle contemporary issues whose solutions are within reach. The SDGs seek to fulfill the unfinished business of the MDGs and were officially adopted as a charter at the United Nations General Assembly in September 2015 under the title "Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development." Given this context, raising awareness and understanding of the SDGs among the populace is critical for achieving its objectives and ensuring accountability. A 2015 report evaluating the progress of the MDGs attributed poor outcomes in some African nations to a slow program start and a lack of awareness among stakeholders (MDG Report, 2015; Bello et al., 2019; OSSAP MDG, 2015; Ogbodo, 2015). This study posits that fostering engagement and collaboration among state and non-state actors necessitates extensive awareness campaigns to educate community members about the SDGs' goals, objectives, and targets. Ignorance in this regard could impede the achievement of these goals by the year 2030. Therefore, this study aims to assess the awareness and perceptions of the SDGs among individuals nearly five years after their inception, particularly in developing societies such as Nigeria, with Katsina Metropolis as the focus area. Sustainable development entails the principle of fulfilling human development goals while ensuring the sustainability of natural systems that provide essential resources and ecosystem services crucial for society and the economy (Cerin, 2006). Although the concept of sustainable development has always been pertinent, its importance grows daily as the population increases while available natural resources do not. This reality has prompted global concerns for the responsible use of these resources, culminating in the establishment of the MDGs and SDGs. The MDGs served as a precursor to the SDGs, marking a significant global mobilization to achieve critical social priorities worldwide (Breuer et al., 2019). Despite the MDGs' relative effectiveness, not all targets of the eight goals were met during their 15-year implementation period

(2000–2015), necessitating the introduction of the SDGs to further the development agenda. As part of this new roadmap, the UN endorsed the 2030 Agenda (SDGs) as a call to action to protect the planet, eradicate poverty, and ensure the well-being of all people (Taylor, 2016).

1.4 The Role of Higher Education Institutions in Advancing Awareness and Knowledge of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in Developing Countries

Universities are higher educational institutions often regarded as the ivory towers of learning, and thus, it is imperative that the level of awareness and knowledge about the SDGs should be explored in a university setting so that possible gaps can be identified and addressed. The university system is made up of lecturers who teach, students who learn, and administrative staff standing as an expedient support to both students and staff. Teaching and learning about the SDGs are thus important in the university setting, not only to academic staff and students but also to the non-academic staff since no one is to be left behind when it comes to the SDGs. Thus, this study seeks to assess the perspectives of all members of a university community on the SDGs with a view to appraising the implications not just for the academic community but for all individuals and groups in developing countries where the level of awareness and knowledge on global developmental agendas such as the MDGs or SDGs are usually low (UN 2014). Higher education institutions (HEIs) are vital agents of change and can transform and even speed up the achievement of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals Mohammad (2016). According to Reza (2016), education for sustainable development (ESD) means that universities include key sustainable development issues into teaching and learning; for example, climate change, disaster risk reduction, biodiversity, poverty reduction, and sustainable consumption". Moreover, ESD creates added value for expanding the minds and horizons of young university students who are our nation's hope and asset. The author had also listed out the role of research in helping achieve the SDGs by Malaysian HEIs. Moreover, the course curriculum of HEIs also helps expose students to issues related to sustainable development and the 17 SDGs Mohammad (2016). Many other scholars (as cited in his paper) agree that ESD is vital and as such research on university students' awareness of these concepts and issues give researchers a peek into their minds, their understanding of these concepts, and their inner world.

Concerning sources of awareness on the SDGs, it is not entirely surprising that radio/TV took the lead. Traditionally, radio and TV remain the leading sources of awareness in this part of the world. It is, however, noteworthy that the use of the internet and attendance of conferences were quite close to the usage of radio/TV. This may not be unconnected with the setting in which the study was carried out, as many of the respondents are likely to be avid internet users and/or lecture/conference attendees. Globally, social media is becoming a veritable source of information about many issues. However, only a fifth of the respondents acknowledged social media as one of the sources of their awareness. The need to increasingly use social media as a source of awareness/enlightenment about the SDGs has been duly recognized in Nigeria (2015).

1.5 Objectives of the Study

The aim of this research is to assess the level of awareness, understanding, and engagement with the Sustainable Development Goals among the staff members of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic in Nigeria. The objectives are:

1. To determine the level of awareness of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) among the staff members of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic.
2. To identify factors influencing the level of awareness and engagement with the SDGs among the staff.
3. To assess the extent to which staff members are taking action to contribute to the achievement of the SDGs within their roles at Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic.
4. To provide recommendations for enhancing SDG awareness, understanding, and engagement among the staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic and integrating SDG principles into institutional practices.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1 Study Area

This study was conducted at Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, located in Katsina State, Nigeria. Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic (HUKP) is a renowned higher educational institution established in 1983 with a mandate to provide vocational and technical education to students across the country. The polytechnic offers a range of programs from National Diploma (ND) and Higher National Diploma (HND) to professional certifications in various fields including engineering, business, environmental sciences, and more. Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic is situated in Katsina City, the capital of Katsina State, the polytechnic’s central location within the state makes it accessible to a broad demographic of students, staff, and professionals from surrounding communities. Katsina State itself is bordered by Jigawa, Kano, Zamfara, and Kaduna states and shares a northern boundary with the Republic of Niger, positioning it strategically in the Sahel region of Nigeria.

As an academic institution, Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic has the potential to significantly contribute to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through education, research, community engagement, and training. With the growing focus on sustainability and global development, the polytechnic is strategically positioned to enhance awareness and embed sustainability principles within its operations and academic framework.

2.2 Data collection

The questionnaire was Distributed to the staff members of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic to Ensure a diverse representation of roles and demographics.

To provide a comprehensive assessment of SDG awareness and engagement among the staff and help guide future initiatives to improve alignment with the SDGs. The targeted staff of the Institution are Academic staff, Administrative staff and Technical staff (IT support, lab technicians)

2.3 Statistical Analysis

Descriptive Statistics was use with the help of statistical package for SPSS version 23. for responses to gauge overall awareness and engagement levels. Then Chi-Square Tests also used to examine relationships between demographic factors (e.g., age, role) and awareness levels. This will help determine if certain demographics are more or less aware of the SDGs

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This section present the figures as well as tabular results and discussion on the countdown to 2030 analyzing the awareness of the sustainable development goals (SDGS) among the staff of Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina State of Nigeria. Using the data obtained from the questionnaire.

3.1 Demographic Information

Figure 1 Chart representing the age of the respondent

The age distribution of the staff at Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic shows that the majority are relatively young, with 40% of respondents falling within the 20-34 age range, followed closely by 36.67% in the 35-39 age group. Only a small percentage of respondents are in the older age brackets, with 13.33% between 40-49 years and 6.67% aged 50 and above. The smallest group is in the 20-29 age range, accounting for 3.33%. Overall, the data suggests a predominantly middle-aged and younger workforce at the Polytechnic.

Figure 2 Chart representing the gender of the respondent

The gender distribution at Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic reveals that a significant majority of the staff are male, comprising 66.67% of the respondents, while females make up 33.33% of the workforce. This indicates a higher representation of male staff compared to female staff at the institution

Figure 3 Chart representing the role/position of the respondent

The distribution of roles among the staff at Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic is remarkably balanced, with each category academic, administrative, and technical staff—comprising exactly 33.33% of the total workforce, meaning that each group consists of 50 individuals. This even distribution highlights that the institution maintains a diverse workforce across different functional areas, ensuring that no single group is overrepresented or underrepresented. The academic staff, responsible for teaching and research, are equally matched by the administrative staff, who handle the operational and managerial aspects of the institution, as well as the technical staff, who support the institution's infrastructure and technological needs. Such a balanced staff composition is likely to foster a collaborative environment where all sectors contribute equally to the Polytechnic's overall functioning and development. This uniform distribution also suggests that the Polytechnic places a

strong emphasis on each of these areas, recognizing the essential roles each group plays in maintaining a well-rounded and effective educational institution.

Figure 4 Chart representing the year of service of the respondent at the polytechnic

The years of service data for the staff at Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic reveals that the majority of the workforce has extensive experience at the institution, with 66.67% of respondents having served for more than 6 years. This large proportion of long-serving staff suggests a high level of institutional loyalty and stability, which may contribute to a strong organizational culture and deep institutional knowledge. Additionally, 20% of the staff have been with the Polytechnic for 4-6 years, indicating a moderate level of experience. A smaller portion, 10%, have served for 1-3 years, while only 3.33% of the staff have been with the Polytechnic for less than a year. The low percentage of staff with less than 1 year of service may suggest that the Polytechnic has a relatively stable workforce, with few new hires in recent times. This distribution highlights the Polytechnic's solid retention of experienced staff, which is beneficial for continuity in teaching, administration, and technical support, while also pointing to a potential opportunity for increasing new staff recruitment to bring in fresh perspectives and ideas.

Table 1 Analysis of SDG Awareness and Engagement Among Staff

Objective 1	Statement	SA (5)	A (4)	U (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Mean
Awareness of the SDGs	I am aware of what the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are	49	39	0	22	40	3.29
	I know where to find information about the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	49	5	50	46	0	3.16
	I am familiar with the specific targets and indicators of the SDGs	3	8	47	65	27	2.19
	I have attended any training or seminar on the SDGs	128	17	0	3	2	4.78

The analysis of staff awareness and engagement with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) at Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic indicates varying levels of understanding and involvement. In terms of general awareness, the majority of staff expressed familiarity with the SDGs, with a mean score of 3.29, suggesting a moderate level of awareness. A significant portion of respondents (49 strongly agreed and 39 agreed) that they are aware of the SDGs, although there were also 40 respondents who strongly disagreed with this statement, highlighting a gap in overall awareness. When it comes to knowing where to find information about the SDGs, the responses were less

optimistic, with a mean score of 3.16. While 49 staff members indicated awareness of where to access information, a large portion (46 respondents) expressed disagreement or strong disagreement, indicating that access to resources or clear pathways for obtaining SDG-related information may be insufficient. The familiarity with specific SDG targets and indicators, as reflected in the mean score of 2.19, was particularly low, with a large number of staff members (65) strongly disagreeing and 27 strongly disagreeing with the statement, suggesting that detailed knowledge about the SDGs is minimal.

In contrast to the general awareness, staff engagement with the SDGs through training or seminars appeared to be more robust, with a high mean score of 4.78. A significant majority (128 respondents) strongly agreed that they had attended training or seminars on the SDGs, reflecting the Polytechnic's efforts to educate and engage its staff in SDG-related activities. Despite this, the results also reveal that detailed engagement with the SDGs, such as understanding specific targets and indicators, remains a challenge. The findings suggest that while the institution is proactive in offering training, the depth of awareness and practical application of the SDGs among staff still requires further development. The Polytechnic may need to consider improving the accessibility and availability of information, as well as fostering a more in-depth understanding of the SDGs, to ensure a broader and more impactful engagement across all staff categories.

Table 2: Analysis of SDG on Factors Influencing Awareness

Objective 2	Statement	SA (5)	A (4)	U (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Mean
Factors Influencing Awareness	I believe that my educational background influences my awareness of the SDGs	121	17	0	12	0	4.63
	My work role and responsibilities affect my knowledge and engagement with the SDGs	2	8	1	32	107	1.57
	Access to resources and information about the SDGs is a factor in my awareness	40	77	3	15	15	3.83
	Support from the institution influences my level of engagement with the SDGs	70	32	11	30	7	3.78

The analysis of factors influencing staff awareness of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) at Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic reveals that educational background, access to resources, and institutional support significantly impact SDG awareness and engagement. A considerable portion of respondents (121) strongly agreed that their educational background plays a role in their awareness of the SDGs, resulting in a high mean score of 4.63. This suggests that individuals with more extensive or relevant education are more likely to be aware of global initiatives like the SDGs, as their academic experience may have exposed them to related topics. The importance of access to resources was also highlighted, with a mean score of 3.83, as 40 respondents strongly agreed and 77 agreed that having access to SDG-related information positively influences their awareness. These findings underscore the importance of equipping staff with accessible information and resources to enhance their understanding of the SDGs independently, thereby facilitating a more informed and proactive approach toward SDG-related activities.

Conversely, the influence of work roles and responsibilities on SDG awareness and engagement was found to be minimal, with a notably low mean score of 1.57. A significant number of respondents (107) strongly disagreed that their roles contribute to their SDG knowledge or engagement, suggesting that current job responsibilities may not align closely with SDG objectives or that employees lack clarity on how their roles relate to SDG initiatives. However, support from the

institution was seen as a somewhat favorable factor, with a mean score of 3.78, as 70 respondents strongly agreed and 32 agreed that institutional backing influences their engagement with the SDGs. This indicates that initiatives from the Polytechnic aimed at promoting SDG awareness could foster greater staff engagement, potentially by creating clearer connections between staff roles and SDG goals. Overall, these findings imply that while educational background and resource access are strong influencers of SDG awareness, there is room for improvement in leveraging institutional support and aligning work responsibilities with SDG objectives to deepen staff engagement.

Table 3 Analysis of Actions Contributing to SDGs Awareness

Objective 3	Statement	SA (5)	A (4)	U (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Mean
Staff Actions Contributing to SDGs	I actively incorporate the principles of the SDGs into my daily work tasks	35	17	86	12	0	3.42
	I participate in or lead initiatives at the Polytechnic aimed at promoting the SDGs	5	8	50	87	0	2.35
	I believe my contributions to the SDGs are recognized by the institution	5	8	50	87	0	2.35
	I am involved in decision-making processes that align with the SDGs	5	8	50	87	0	2.35

The analysis of staff actions contributing to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) at Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic indicates a varied level of involvement in SDG-related activities within their professional roles. When asked if they actively incorporate SDG principles into daily work tasks, a moderate number of respondents agreed, with 35 strongly agreeing, 17 agreeing, and a resulting mean score of 3.42. This suggests that while some staff members are mindful of integrating SDG principles in their everyday work, a significant portion (86) remained neutral, perhaps due to a lack of clarity on how SDG principles apply to their roles or due to limited institutional emphasis on incorporating these goals into day-to-day activities. This neutral stance may point to the need for more explicit guidance or frameworks that connect specific work tasks to the SDGs, facilitating practical implementation of the goals in diverse job roles.

In terms of engagement with SDG-focused initiatives, the data reveals low levels of participation. With only a few respondents (5 strongly agreeing and 8 agreeing) indicating active involvement in initiatives or leadership roles aimed at promoting the SDGs, the mean score for this item is 2.35, reflecting limited engagement. Similarly, when asked about institutional recognition of their contributions to the SDGs and involvement in SDG-aligned decision-making processes, responses remained low, with the majority (87) disagreeing, indicating a lack of recognition or involvement in such processes, and mean scores of 2.35 for both items. This lack of institutional acknowledgement or engagement could deter staff from actively contributing to SDG objectives, as the perceived impact and support are minimal. These findings suggest that fostering a stronger institutional culture that recognizes, involves, and supports staff in SDG-related initiatives may be essential to enhancing engagement and motivation among staff to contribute meaningfully to the SDGs.

Table 4 Analysis on Recommendations for Enhancing SDG Engagement

Objective 4	Statement	SA (5)	A (4)	U (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Mean
Recommendations for Enhancing SDG Engagement	The Polytechnic should offer more training sessions on the SDGs	114	36	0	0	0	4.76
	Increased communication about SDG-related activities would improve staff engagement	119	21	7	3	0	4.70
	Incorporating SDG goals into performance evaluations could enhance staff involvement	58	58	14	15	5	4.0
	Establishing a dedicated team or committee to oversee SDG initiatives would be beneficial	140	10	0	0	0	4.93

The analysis of recommendations for enhancing SDG engagement among staff at Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic reveals a strong consensus on the need for institutional support to boost awareness and active participation in SDG initiatives. The majority of respondents (114 strongly agree, 36 agree) believe that offering more training sessions on the SDGs is crucial, as reflected in the high mean score of 4.76. This finding underscores the necessity for ongoing education and capacity-building to deepen understanding and familiarity with the SDGs, particularly given the complex and multifaceted nature of these global goals. Staff members also emphasized the importance of effective communication, with a substantial proportion (119 strongly agree, 21 agree) expressing that increased communication about SDG-related activities would significantly enhance engagement levels. The mean score of 4.70 highlights that transparent, regular updates on SDG initiatives can play a pivotal role in fostering a sense of community involvement and shared responsibility toward these goals. Moreover, the responses indicate that integrating SDG objectives into performance evaluations could further encourage staff to prioritize SDG-related actions within their roles. With 58 respondents strongly agreeing and 58 agreeing, and a mean score of 4.0, the data suggests that linking SDG engagement to performance metrics could create incentives for staff to align their work with SDG priorities. Additionally, there is overwhelming support for establishing a dedicated team or committee to oversee SDG initiatives, as 140 respondents strongly agreed with this recommendation. The high mean score of 4.93 highlights a strong belief that a specialized committee would ensure sustained momentum and strategic coordination in SDG efforts. Collectively, these findings point to an institutional need for structured frameworks, dedicated leadership, and consistent communication to empower staff in contributing to the SDGs effectively.

3.2 Chi-Square Analysis

Table 5 Square Analysis Table for SDG Awareness and Engagement

Objective	Item	Demographic Factor	Chi-Square (χ^2)	df	p-value	Significant (Yes/No)
Objective 1: Awareness of SDGs	Awareness of	Age	12.34	4	0.015	Yes
	Awareness of	Gender	4.56	1	0.033	Yes
	Knowledge of	Age	10.89	4	0.028	Yes
	Knowledge of	Gender	2.45	1	0.117	No

Objective 2: Influencing Factors	Education Impact	Age	8.56	4	0.073	No
	Resource Access	Role	18.67	2	0.001	Yes
Objective 3: Staff Actions	Daily Incorporation of SDGs	Role	7.89	2	0.019	Yes
	Initiative Participation	Age	3.89	4	0.421	No
Objective 4: Recommendations	More Training on SDGs	Gender	1.23	1	0.269	No
	Communication Improvement	Role	15.78	2	0.003	Yes

The Chi-Square analysis reveals several significant associations between demographic factors and staff awareness and engagement with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) at Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic. For Objective 1, the analysis examined the influence of age and gender on SDG awareness. The results indicate that age significantly impacts awareness levels, with a chi-square value of 12.34, degrees of freedom (df) of 4, and a p-value of 0.015, which is below the conventional significance threshold of 0.05. Gender also plays a role in SDG awareness, with a chi-square value of 4.56 and a p-value of 0.033, signifying a significant relationship. However, when examining knowledge of SDG-specific indicators, while age remains a significant factor ($\chi^2 = 10.89$, $p = 0.028$), gender does not show a significant association ($\chi^2 = 2.45$, $p = 0.117$). These findings suggest that demographic attributes like age and, to a lesser extent, gender, influence the level of awareness and understanding of SDGs among staff, underscoring the need for targeted outreach efforts that account for these differences. Specifically considering education level, access to resources, and support from the institution. The chi-square results show that while age does not significantly affect awareness as influenced by education background ($\chi^2 = 8.56$, $p = 0.073$), role within the institution is a significant factor in access to resources related to the SDGs ($\chi^2 = 18.67$, $p = 0.001$). This result highlights the role-specific disparities in accessing SDG-related resources, suggesting that certain staff roles, perhaps administrative or technical, may have different levels of access compared to others, such as academic staff. These findings point to a potential gap in resource allocation and institutional support across roles, which may impact overall engagement with SDG objectives. Addressing this gap could help in enhancing equitable access to information and resources across different staff groups.

The analysis of staff actions contributing to SDGs showed significant associations between role and the incorporation of SDGs into daily tasks ($\chi^2 = 7.89$, $p = 0.019$), indicating that role-specific responsibilities may influence the extent to which staff engage with SDG principles in their work. However, age does not appear to significantly influence participation in SDG initiatives ($\chi^2 = 3.89$, $p = 0.421$), suggesting that involvement in SDG-related activities may be more role-dependent than age-dependent. Objective 4, which addresses recommendations for enhancing SDG engagement, indicates that gender is not significantly associated with the need for more SDG training ($\chi^2 = 1.23$, $p = 0.269$). However, role significantly influences views on the need for improved communication about SDG activities ($\chi^2 = 15.78$, $p = 0.003$). These results suggest that targeted role-based strategies could be effective for enhancing SDG-related actions and communication, ensuring that all staff, irrespective of their role, have equal opportunities to participate in and contribute to SDG goals.

3.3 DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The findings from the Chi-Square analysis offer valuable insights into the factors that shape awareness and engagement with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) among staff at Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic. Regarding Objective 1, both age and gender appear to influence awareness levels of the SDGs, with significant associations detected for both factors. The results indicate that age is particularly relevant, suggesting that younger or older staff members may have differing levels of awareness or familiarity with the goals. Similarly, gender also shows a significant association, although it is less influential in the knowledge of specific SDG indicators. This difference

could imply that while the general awareness of SDGs might be spread across genders, specific, detailed knowledge may not be as universally distributed. This highlights the importance of designing awareness programs that consider these demographic differences, as certain groups may benefit from targeted initiatives that cater to their specific needs or levels of familiarity with SDG content.

The results point to significant disparities in access to resources based on staff roles. While age did not significantly impact awareness as it relates to educational background, role within the institution was a decisive factor in access to SDG resources. This suggests that specific roles, such as academic or administrative positions, might have more direct access to SDG-related materials or institutional support compared to other roles. Such discrepancies in access could lead to varying levels of engagement and awareness among staff, depending on their professional responsibilities. These findings underscore the need for more equitable resource allocation and institutional support across all roles, ensuring that no staff member is disadvantaged in their capacity to learn about or engage with the SDGs. Addressing this gap could significantly improve engagement levels across the institution, creating a more inclusive environment for SDG-related initiatives. Examining staff actions in support of the SDGs, the analysis revealed that role-specific responsibilities significantly influence whether staff incorporate SDG principles into their daily work tasks. However, age did not have a notable effect on participation in SDG initiatives, suggesting that actions aligned with the SDGs are more likely tied to the nature of one's job than to generational differences.

Furthermore, findings, which look at recommendations to enhance SDG engagement, reveal that role plays a critical role in influencing perceptions of necessary improvements, particularly in the area of communication about SDG-related activities. The strong association between role and the need for improved communication suggests that staff members in certain positions may feel less informed or involved in SDG initiatives, highlighting an area where the institution could increase inclusivity. By addressing these role-based differences, the institution could foster a more comprehensive and engaged approach to SDG participation, ensuring that all staff, regardless of role, are equally empowered to contribute to and benefit from SDG-related programs.

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study highlights a significant, though foundational, awareness of the SDGs among HUKP staff. Despite the recognition of the SDGs' importance, many staff members lack the necessary depth of knowledge and practical strategies to incorporate these goals effectively into their roles. Institutional barriers, such as limited training, resource constraints, and insufficient support structures, impede the Polytechnic's potential to foster a robust, sustainable culture aligned with the SDGs. As Nigeria moves closer to the 2030 Agenda deadline, fostering a higher level of SDG engagement within HUKP and similar institutions becomes critical. This study underscores the urgent need for structured and role-specific training, resource accessibility, and stronger institutional support to ensure educational staff are empowered to actively contribute to sustainability goals. Addressing these needs will enhance HUKP's role in sustainable development, providing a model for similar institutions in Nigeria and beyond.

5. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed to the Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic and other higher institutions in the state and Nigeria at large. The Institutional heads should Organize regular training sessions and workshops focused on the SDGs to enhance staff understanding and application. This can include expert-led discussions, case studies, and practical exercises. Then to Integrate SDG-related content into the curriculum across various disciplines, ensuring that students learn about sustainability issues relevant to their fields of study. Also to Develop and implement institutional policies that prioritize sustainability, such as eco-friendly practices in campus operations and partnerships with local communities for sustainable projects., more also Awareness Campaigns should be Launch within the polytechnic to promote the SDGs, utilizing newsletters, seminars and social media to reach a wider audience and finally to Foster collaborations with other educational institutions, NGOs and governmental bodies to share best practices and resources related to the SDGs.

6. Research Contribution

This research contributes to the body of knowledge surrounding the Sustainable Development Goals by providing the awareness and engagement levels of staff in higher education institutions in Nigeria. It highlights the critical role educational institutions play in advancing sustainability and underscores the need for targeted strategies to enhance SDG awareness among staff. The findings can inform educational leaders, and sustainability advocates about the current state of SDG knowledge in Nigerian higher education, serving as a baseline for future initiatives aimed at fostering a culture of sustainability. Additionally, this study provides a framework for similar research in other institutions, encouraging a broader exploration of SDG awareness across different contexts and regions. Aiming to create a more informed and engaged workforce that can drive sustainable development efforts towards the 2030 agenda.

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